

Prime Number Correlation Conjecture

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Conjecture text

This conjecture defines numerical values capable of correlating prime numbers. These coefficients (V_i) are referred to as '**Correlation nodes of the prime numbers**'.

Given the set of natural numbers \mathbb{N} such that $\{\forall x_i \in \mathbb{N}\}$. Let us define the operator T_i which produces the sum of all digits of the number to which it is applied, in one or more cycles, until a p-value is obtained such that $1 \leq p \leq 9$. Let x_i be progressive prime numbers greater than 10;

- The first group is characterised by $T_i(x_i) = 1$ or 4 or 7.
- The second group is characterised by $T_i(x_i) = 2$ or 5 or 8.

Let us consider the notation j as the last digit of a number x_i such that $x_i \in \mathbb{N}$. Given $\{\forall x_i \in \mathbb{N} \mid T_i(x_i) \neq 3, 6, 9 \mid j \neq 2 \text{ or } 5 \text{ or } 0\}$

Consider also the factor C given by the sum of the numbers 2, 3, 5 and 7. Consider the value d which can take values between 0 and $+\infty$.

Two distinct and complementary mathematical correlations can be defined between the two sets of prime numbers.

a) First correlation

if

$$(i) \quad T_i(x_i) = 1 \text{ o } 4 \text{ o } 7$$

than

$$(ii) \quad V_i = T_i(\sum_{i=1}^{1+3d} T_i(x_i) + C) = 9 \text{ o } 6 \text{ o } 3$$

Example

Table 1 shows the calculation of the V_i parameter step by step for the group of prime numbers $x_i | T(x_i) = 1$ or 4 or 7 .

Table 1: Calculation steps useful for obtaining the values of the 'Prime number correlation nodes' for the group having $T_i(x_i)$ values of 1 or 4 or 7 .

Chiave 1-4-7					
C=C1+C2+C3+C4					
i	Numero primo	Ti(xi)	Somm(T(xi)+C)	Ti(Somm(T(xi)+C)	Vi
C1	2	2			
C2	3	3			
C3	5	5			
C4	7	7			
1	13	4	21	3	3
2	19	1	22	4	
3	31	4	26	8	
4	37	1	27	9	9
5	43	7	34	7	
6	61	7	41	5	
7	67	4	45	9	9
8	73	1	46	1	
9	79	7	53	8	
10	97	7	60	3	3
11	103	4	64	1	
12	109	1	65	2	
13	127	1	66	3	3
14	139	4	70	7	
15	181	1	71	8	
16	193	4	75	3	3
17	229	4	79	7	
18	241	7	86	5	
19	283	4	90	9	9
20	307	1	91	1	
21	313	7	98	8	
22	331	7	105	6	6
23	337	4	109	1	
24	349	7	116	8	
25	367	7	123	6	6
26	373	4	127	1	
27	397	1	128	2	
28	409	4	132	6	6

The key nodes V_i of correlation of prime numbers are highlighted in yellow. Note that the sum of the values $T_i(\text{Somm}(T(x_i)+C))$ between the key nodes also returns a value between 3 or 6 or 9.

a) Second correlation

if

$$(iii) \quad T_i(x_i) = 2 \text{ o } 5 \text{ o } 8$$

then

$$(iv) \quad V_i = T_i(\sum_{i=1}^{2+3d} T_i(x_i) + C) = 9 \text{ o } 6 \text{ o } 3$$

Example

Table 2 illustrates the calculation of the V_i parameter step by step for the group of prime numbers $x_i \mid T(x_i) = 2 \text{ or } 5 \text{ or } 8$.

Table 2: Calculation steps useful for obtaining the values of the 'Prime number correlation nodes' for the group having $T_i(x_i)$ values of 2 or 5 or 8.

Chiave 5-8-2					
C=C1+C2+C3+C4					
i	Numero primo	$T_i(x_i)$	Somm($T(x_i)+C$)	$T_i(\text{Somm}(T(x_i)+C))$	V_i
C1		2	2		
C2		3	3		
C3		5	5		
C4		7	7		
	1	11	2	19	1
	2	17	8	27	9
	3	23	5	32	5
	4	29	2	34	7
	5	41	5	39	3
	6	47	2	41	5
	7	53	8	49	4
	8	59	5	54	9
	9	71	8	62	8
	10	83	2	64	1
	11	89	8	72	9
	12	131	5	77	5
	13	137	2	79	7
	14	149	5	84	3
	15	173	2	86	5
	16	179	8	94	4
	17	191	2	96	6
	18	197	8	104	5
	19	233	8	112	4
	20	239	5	117	9
	21	251	8	125	8
	22	257	5	130	4
	23	281	2	132	6
	24	257	5	137	2
	25	281	2	139	4
	26	293	5	144	9
	27	311	5	149	5
	28	317	2	151	7
	29	347	5	156	3
	30	353	2	158	5
	31	359	8	166	4
	32	383	5	171	9

The values V_i defined as key correlation nodes of prime numbers are highlighted in yellow.

Note that the sum of the values $T_i(\text{Somm}(T(x_i)+C))$ between the key nodes also returns a value between 3 or 6 or 9.